

Correlation between electrical resistivity and temperature and the impact of the seawater flow in the Asal rift, Republic of Djibouti

Abdek Hassan Aden¹, Jasmin Raymond¹, Bernard Giroux¹

¹ Institut national de la recherche scientifique, Québec, Canada
abdek.hassan_aden@ete.inrs.ca

Keywords: Correlation, hydrothermal, temperature and resistivity

Abstract

The main parameters influencing the variation of electrical resistivity in a rift context are temperature, the presence of fluids, the existence of hydrothermal alteration minerals and lithology. These parameters are mainly controlled by the volcanic and tectonic activity that determines the geological structure of the rift and the behavior of the associated hydrothermal system. Determining the predominant parameters that affect the electrical resistivity and its degree of influence over the other parameters is often tedious and sometimes subject to different interpretations, depending on the available data.

1. Introduction

The Magnetotelluric (MT) method has become a standard geophysical technique for subsurface exploration of geothermal fields. The evaluation of the Earth electrical conductivity allows to infer areas preferential to fluid flow. The objectives of this study are to advance the MT method by establishing a correlation between the variation of the temperature and electrical conductivity at depth, and to use the method to better understand how seawater flow influences the thermal behavior of hydrothermal systems in the Asal rift.

2. Methods and techniques

A series of 1D models of electrical resistivity will be developed from the inversion of MT data collected at 81 stations. A first correlation between the temperature profiles measured in geothermal wells and the variation in electrical resistivity of the stations closer to these boreholes will be performed. Then, a second correlation between the electrical resistivity and the estimated proportion of smectite in the drilling logs will be developed, since a high proportion of smectite is often interpreted as the cap rock of a geothermal reservoir.

Finally, a 2D multiphase flow model will be developed taking into account the regional groundwater flow with seawater that seeps through the open fractures of the Asal rift towards Asal Lake having an elevation difference of 153 m. Then, the influence of a magmatic heat source

triggering the activation of hydrothermal systems overlying the regional flow will be evaluated.

3. Results and discussion

Our 1D model resistivity shows a good correlation between electrical resistivity and temperature profile measured in geothermal wells (Fig. 1). So, we infer the existence of two aquifers: the intermediate geothermal reservoir and the deep reservoir (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2). The recharge and feeding of these aquifers come mainly from three types of sources: seawater, rainfall and water from Lake Asal. Generally, the water of hot springs of the Asal lake come from the varying degrees interaction of these three types of sources with the host rocks (basalts).

On the basis of the geochemical data, the initial fluid of hot springs located at North and South West of Lake Asal appears to be of meteoric origin. It is important to note also that some sources that are located North and South west of Asal Lake have an initial fluid that comes partially from Lake Asal (Sanjuan 1990). A marine initial fluid feeds the hot springs in the axial part of the rift. This fluid, from the sea of Ghoubbet to Lake Asal, flows with high velocity into open fractures and fractures of the Asal rift (Mlynarski and al. 2001). The thermal anomaly beneath Asal rift increase the temperature of this fluid. Due the topography difference between the sea and the lake and properties of host rock, the hot springs are the evidence of this regional outflow.

Fig. 1 Correlation between resistivity model and temperature profile measured in Asal 5.

Given the high salinity of Lake Asal and geochemical data, 90% of the water supply to Lake Asal is through this source of marine water.

The subsurface electrical conductivity of the region is mainly controlled by the groundwater flow and high heat flow under rift. We suggest that an intermediate reservoir exist and is associated with the low value around 1 ohm.m of electrical resistivity model between 500 and 1000 m of depth correspond the decrease of temperature profile that confirm the circulation of cold seawater. The increase of electrical resistivity under 1300 m and the correspond linearly geothermal gradient can be interpreted that the heat transfer is mainly dominated by conduction in the rocks and there is any advection as confirm by drillings results of well Asal 5. The decrease of the electrical resistivity under 4000 m of depth (**Fig. 2**), may be due the presence of molten rock (Dobre et al. 2007) or a deep groundwater flow in permeable volcanic rocks.

Fig. 2 Inversion model of the electrical resistivity of the closer MT station of Asal 5

4. Conclusions

Two geothermal reservoirs have been identified in the Asal rift by previous studies. Our results will clarify the role of the interpretation of the electrical resistivity in the characterization of the hydrothermal system and the understanding of the temporal evolution of the circulation of the sea water with the numerical modeling of multiphase flow and heat transfer.

Acknowledgments

We are acknowledged Dr. Bernard Sanjuan (BRGM), Gatien Sakindi (Electricity Company of Rwanda), Abdourahman Haga and Djama Robleh (Ministry of Energy and Natural Ressources of the Republic Djibouti) who contributed to this project. We also thank the IDB and the INRS for the scholarship of this project doctoral.

References

- Dobre, C., Peltzer, G. (2007), "Fluid-controlled faulting process in the Asal rift, Djibouti, from 8 yr of radar interferometry observations", *Geology*, 35(1), 69-72
- Mlynarski, M., Zlotnicki, J. (2001), "Fluid circulation in the active emerged Asal rift (east Africa, Djibouti) inferred from self-potential and Telluric-Telluric prospecting", *Tectonophysics*, 339(3-4), 455-472
- Sanjuan, B., Michard, G., Michard, A. (1990), "Origine des substances dissoutes dans les eaux des sources thermales et des forages de la région Asal-Ghoubbet (République de Djibouti)", *J. Volcanol. Geotherm. Res.*, 43(1-4), 333-352